

FREELANCING PLATFORM FOR WOMEN AND GIRLS

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Annotation: GiTECH Website is a specialized platform aimed at empowering and supporting women pursuing freelance careers in the technology sector. By providing a wide range of resources, networking opportunities, and mentorship, the website creates a community for like-minded women to thrive as freelancers in the tech industry. This platform plays a key role in promoting gender diversity and inclusion, helping to close the gender gap in the technology-driven freelance market. The functionality of GiTECH is as follows: **Curated Job Opportunities:** A dedicated job board featuring curated freelance tech opportunities enables users to find and apply for projects that match their skills and interests. **Networking Opportunities:** The website offers various networking events, both online and in-person, to help female tech freelancers connect, share knowledge, and build a supportive network. **Focused Support:** The platform specifically targets women in the tech industry, providing tailored resources and fostering a sense of community and collaboration.

Key words: Website, Women, Freelance careers, Vacancies, Technology sector, Tech industry, Gender diversity, Gender gap, Courses, Community, Collaboration.

Introduction. At present, technology is developing day by day. In order to facilitate people's life, many experts are trying to create new technologies, application

and different projects for different purposes. After pandemic years, in the year between 2019 and 2022, people started working remote, as it was not allowed and was not safe for people to go outside often. Because of this, everybody started freelancing and working from home. At many people mainly learnt IT skills including WEB, ANDROID, IOS DEVELOPMENT, etc. Because these skills can be learnt online with the help of internet, and with these skills one can work remotely and make a living. In the past also, the numbers of software developers were high, but now this rate is increasing noticeably. Due to this, many platforms are being built for developers to find remote job.

As IT started coming to Uzbekistan recently, the number of IT companies and IT job platforms are low. So, in an effort to make a contribution for the development of Uzbekistan, we decided to form a platform and a company for those who are interested in IT. Our project is mainly for girls and called GiTECH. Here, in Uzbekistan, for women and girls it is a bit difficult to go outside and work. Taking this into consideration, we decided to build a web application which can help females to find remote job easily based on their knowledge and experience. If they are experienced enough, they can see so many job vacancies as a senior or junior developer depending on their skills, otherwise if they do not have adequate experience there will be also internship vacancies. Those who do not have any skill but have interest can see suggested courses and guidelines for becoming a great software developer. If they complete those courses successfully, they will have the opportunity to work from home in a company.

What is different in our application as compared to other application and platforms is that it is only for girls. The reason why we specialized this app only for girls is that the number of female developers is lower than males. As we mentioned before, women stay usually at home in Uzbekistan, and we thought that software development is the best job position for females. Thus, in order to help women and girls to find their desired job, we decided to build a web application which can give

many ways to find job vacancies, courses, guidelines which all will be helpful for the self-development of females.

Purpose of Study. If we pay attention to the annual statistics on the Internet, then in our country about 234 thousand girls graduate from school every year, and only 20% of them enter to higher institutions. And what about the rest of other 80%? their future industries and employment are important. It is necessary to provide knowledge in this field, taking into account of their interest and potential in the field of IT. In addition, it is not easy for educated and experienced IT professionals to find a job, because a programmer requires at least 6 months of work experience, and in order to gain such experience, programmers need to do an internship. Many high-paying job and freelance platforms are foreign platforms, and our local job platforms are almost non-existent. But, as we mentioned above, it is somehow difficult for women and girls to go to work. Thus, this Freelance Community project supports Uzbek girls and encourages them to break the stereotypes that “programming is not for girls”.

The goal is to attract Uzbek girls to the field of modern information and communication technologies, create mobile applications, websites, software products, teach them computer design, and help them become programmers. In order to increase their knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies and attract more Uzbek girls - women in need of employment in this field, the GiTECH website will be developed and online registration will be launched.

Through all of that, we have watched the girls in Tech ecosystem flourish across Uzbekistan and grow stronger globally. We strongly believe that the ecosystem of girl-women in tech is stronger when we coordinate and collaborate to ultimately provide the best opportunities for girls in tech.

Methods. GiTECH, a non-profit organization, is dedicated to bridging the gender gap in technology by motivating, instructing, and providing young women with the necessary computing abilities to seize opportunities in the 21st century. To assist girls

on their technological journey, GiTECH offers a variety of programs and resources, such as:

- ❖ **Community:** Assisting women and girls with an interest in the IT field by providing guidance and direction for their future careers based on their preferences, even if they lack prior knowledge or skills.

- ❖ **Remote Work Opportunities:** Information on remote IT job openings tailored to individuals' skills and knowledge levels. Although Girls Who Code doesn't directly link freelancers with clients, it plays a vital part in equipping young women with the skills and self-assurance necessary to thrive in the tech sector, including seeking freelance work.

- ❖ **Networking Events:** Online and in-person events designed to facilitate connections among female freelancers, helping them build a supportive network and learn from each other's experiences.

- ❖ **Mentorship Program:** A structured program that pairs experienced female freelancers with those just starting their journey, providing guidance.

Conclusion. In conclusion, GiTECH is a unique and valuable platform designed to empower and support women in Uzbekistan to pursue remote work opportunities in the technology sector. By providing a range of resources, including job vacancies, internship opportunities, and educational courses, GiTECH aims to bridge the gender gap and encourage more women to succeed in the IT industry, contributing to the overall development of Uzbekistan.

References:

<https://www.tutorialspoint.com/php/index.htm>

<https://www.w3schools.com/php/>

<https://stackoverflow.com/>

<https://laravel.com/>

<https://javascript.info/>